

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D6.2

Annual report on EOSC operation

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
API	Application Programming Interface
COG	Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GSNL	GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
NL	Natural Language
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RO	Research objects
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SLC	Single Look Complex
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
VM	Virtual Machine
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	7
2 Introduction	8
2.1 Scope	8
2.2 Audience	8
2.3 Structure	8
3 Research objects	9
3.1 ROHub	9
3.2 EGI check-in integration	10
3.3 Zenodo and B2Share integration	11
3.4 B2drop integration	13
3.5 ROHub deployment and operations	14
3.5.1 ROHub development instance	14
3.5.2 ROHub production instance	15
3.6 ROHub monitoring/availability	16
3.7 ROHub helpdesk and support channels	17
3.8 Other research object services	19
3.8.1 Checklist service	19
3.8.2 Stability service	21
3.8.3 PDF service	22
4 Data Cubes	23
4.1 User Interfaces and services	23
4.1.1 Explorer	23
4.1.2 JupyterLab	24
4.1.3 Data Access System	24
4.2 Data Cube resources	25
4.3 Cloud resources	26
5 Text Mining and Semantic Enrichment Services	28
5.1 Enrichment service	29
5.1.2 Research object enrichment	32
5.2 Search service	33
5.3 Recommendation service	36
5.5 Cloud resources	37
5.6 Text mining and enrichment services support channel	38
6 Earth Observation Data Pipelines	39
6.1 Data Sourcing	40
6.2 Processing Resources	42
7 Other services	43
7.1 EGI Notebooks	43

7.2 EGI DataHub	44
7.3 VM on demand	45
References	49

1 Executive Summary

RELIANCE, short for Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC, aims to realise the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies:

- Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities, which relies upon the ROHub platform as the reference service;
- Data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access, which relies upon the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform as the reference service;
- Text mining and semantic enrichment services allow the extraction of machine-readable metadata from textual RO resources to enable researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research. The text mining and semantic enrichment services rely on the AI-based natural language processing and understanding platform *expert.ai* as base system.

The services that RELIANCE will integrate into EOSC include:

- ROHub platform providing Research Object management functionalities
- ADAM platform providing Data Cubes management functionalities
- Text Mining services providing functionalities for information extraction and semantic annotation, content-based retrieval and recommendation, as well as extended analytics services
- Copernicus Data Pipelines, an added-value service enabling the systematic execution of Earth Observation (EO) applications to continuously deliver data and information to different users, complying with their specifications for information content and format.

As part of the integration in EOSC, RELIANCE services will leverage and integrate with some of the EOSC core-cross cutting and added value services (as described in this document), playing a complementary role to what is already available and bridging between various EOSC services. RELIANCE will pilot the services in three different Earth Science communities, fostering the use of Copernicus data and demonstrating their efficacy in real-life vertical and multi-disciplinary scenarios.

This report documents the activities undertaken in the past 12 months to offer the project services through the EOSC delivery channels, including the technical and service provisioning integration activities and their status, as well as a report of the helpdesk activities.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope

This annual deliverable will describe the activities undertaken in the past 12 months to offer the project services through the EOSC delivery channels, including the technical and service provisioning integration activities and their status, as well as a report of the helpdesk activities.

2.2 Audience

This deliverable is intended for internal use by the RELIANCE Consortium, although it may be valuable to external stakeholders, including other EOSC related projects who are also dealing with the integration of their services into the EOSC.

2.3 Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 provides a description of activities regarding the integration of Research objects (RO) through the EOSC delivery channels as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities, which relies upon ROHub platform as the reference service;
- Section 4 provides a description of activities regarding Data cubes as the mechanism enabling an efficient scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access, with the integration of the Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform through the EOSC delivery channels;
- Section 5 provides a description of activities regarding text mining and semantic enrichment services through the EOSC delivery channels to allow extracting machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research, and which rely on the AI-based natural language processing and understanding platform *expert.ai* as base system.
- Section 6 provides a description of activities regarding EOSC support to the design and deployment of Copernicus Earth Observation Data Pipelines in order to provide an integrated intermediate service layer for the systematic execution of Earth Observation Applications continuously delivering data and information to users.

3 Research objects

3.1 ROHub

ROHub [1,2] is the main service in RELIANCE providing research object management functionalities. ROHub is a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management and preservation of scientific investigations, campaigns and operational processes via research objects. As part of RELIANCE, a new and enhanced version of the ROHub platform is being released, which integrates new and/or updated services, including RO added value services coming from WP3 and WP4, as well as EOSC services that are being leveraged and reused.

Figure 1 below depicts a high-level view of the ROHub architecture, which was described in detail in D5.2.

Figure 1 ROHub high-level architecture

As depicted in the diagram, ROHub integrates and reuses four EOSC services (one is in progress), including:

- **EGI check-in**, the EOSC Identity and Access Management (IAM) service that operates as a central hub to connect federated Identity Providers (IdPs) with EOSC service providers.
- **Zenodo**, a EOSC catch-all repository that enables researchers, scientists, projects and institutions to share, preserve and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data, software and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities.

- **B2share**, another EOSC catch-all repository that facilitates research data storage, guarantees long-term persistence of data and allows data, results or ideas to be shared worldwide.
- **B2drop** (in progress), an EOSC file storage service on the cloud providing a secure and trusted data exchange service for researchers and scientists to keep their research data synchronised and up-to-date and to exchange them with other researchers.

3.2 EGI check-in integration

The ROHub Identity and Access Management (IAM) is based on Keycloak technology¹. It allows users to authenticate to ROHub and enables single sign-on across different RELIANCE services. Accordingly, other RELIANCE services, such as Data Cubes (ADAM) and Enrichment, allow users to authenticate via ROHub IAM.

ROHub IAM integrates EGI check-in and therefore, it allows the user to authenticate via the EGI check-in service or by providing his/her email and password. If the user selects to login with EGI check-in (see Figure 2), then (s)he can use any of the identity providers supported (see Figure 3), such as the academic institution or one of the social account providers (e.g., orcid, google, Facebook, GitHub, LinkedIn, etc.). After selecting the academic/social identity provider, the user should follow the normal process of the provider to authenticate, providing its username/email and their password (on that provider). After authenticating, the user can edit his user profile information and set other authentication options as described in D5.2.

Figure 2 ROHub login page

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Figure 3 EGI check-in login page

3.3 Zenodo and B2Share integration

As described in detail in D5.2, users are able to publish snapshots/archives of research objects in Zenodo and/or B2Share. The idea is that because of the wider audience of those platforms, publishing research objects there would increase their findability and reuse. Only snapshots/archives are eligible for publishing as they are immutable objects and can be assigned a DOI (see the evolution mechanisms described in D5.2).

Users can publish snapshots/archives of research objects both from the ROHub portal and from the ROHub API library. In the portal, for example, when the user selects “snapshot” or “archive” in the source research object overview page (using the third button in the toolbox as depicted in Figure 4), this will open the create RO wizard, customised to the state selected, allow the user to generate a DOI (provided by ROHub) and/or to publish it in Zenodo/B2Share (as depicted in Figure 5).

PUBLIC MANUAL LIVE DATA RESEARCH OBJECT

EARTH SCIENCES

Created: 08 November 2021 (22:06)

Analysis of MOD_Aqua mass concentration chlorophyll concentration in sea water

Anne Fouilloux

Last modified: 08 November 2021 (22:16)

Description:

This Research Object aggregates the resources associated with the analysis of MOD_Aqua mass concentration chlorophyll concentration in sea water

Sketch:

☆ 0.00 / 5 2 0

8	0
Downloads	Views
Hide more details	
Resources	2
Annotations	12
Events	15
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	103.98 KB

AGENTS
 Raul Palma
 Creator

QUALITY 0%

TOOLBOX

SHARE
 Evolution
 Fork
 Snapshot
 Archive

CITE AS
 Fouilloux, Anne. "Analysis of MOD_Aqua mass c oncentration chlorophyll concentration in sea w ater." ROHub. Nov 08 ,2021. https://w3id.org/ro-i d/9e533d0d-b1de-4b0d-9dd8-14d136aacea5.

Figure 4 Research object evolution mechanisms in ROHub portal

Create new Research Object

Basic information Authors & contributors Tags Sketches gallery Resources Related locations License & Funding Other metadata

Basic information

Title

Analysis of MOD_Aqua mass concentration chlorophyll concentration in sea water

Description

This Research Object aggregates the resources associated with the analysis of MOD_Aqua mass concentration chlorophyll concentration in sea water

Publication services

No Needed B2SHARE ZENODO

Create DOI

Figure 5 Snapshot creation wizard

3.4 B2drop integration

Research objects can aggregate both internal and external resources. An external resources is identified via an URL link to the physical resource, e.g., the URL of a dataset in an institutional or community repository, the URL (or DOI) of a paper in a journal, the URL of a result file in GitHub or Zenodo, etc. An internal resource, on the other hand, is a resource (i.e., file/archive) that is physically uploaded to ROHub. The internal resources are stored in the resource storage used by ROHub. Currently, ROHub supports S3 compatible storages, as depicted in Figure 1, such as Minio², Ceph³, or the Amazon S3 Simple Storage Service⁴.

However, as part of the future work, ROHub will:

- Integrate and support B2Drop as a default resource storage using user credentials (via the user token). This will allow the user to access the resources aggregated by his/her research objects also via the B2Drop dashboard (see Figure 6). In this case, though, the storage limits for the user account in B2Drop will apply, and the internal resources size will count towards this limit. Also, if the user reaches his/her limit in B2Drop, (s)he won't be able to store any additional internal resources.
- Allow the user to select the default storage for internal resources, so that he can choose B2Drop or one of the available S3 storages.

Figure 6 B2Drop user dashboard

² <https://min.io/>

³ <https://ceph.io/en/>

⁴ https://aws.amazon.com/s3/?did=ft_card&trk=ft_card

3.5 ROHub deployment and operations

ROHub is deployed in a PaaS environment at PSNC, which is based on OpenShift Container Platform⁵ and Kubernetes Infrastructure⁶.

There are two instances of ROHub: i) the production instance that has deployed the latest stable version of the service and has all the real research objects stored, and ii) the development instance that has deployed the ongoing additions/updates that are being tested before moving them to a stable version and has only test research objects stored.

In the following we provide a summary of the user endpoints and resources allocated to each instance.

3.5.1 ROHub development instance

Host: <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl>

Version: 2.0.24

Date: 9.01.2022

Browsable API root: <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/api/>

Swagger interface: <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/api/swagger/>

Redoc interface: <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/api/redoc/>

Portal: <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/>

ROHub IAM: <https://keycloak-dev.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/auth/realms/rohub/>

ROHub development uses as default storage for internal resources a minio S3 service (see table below).

Table 1 ROHub resources for development instance

Container	Replicas	Requested Memory	Memory limit	Requested CPU	CPU limit	Storage	Additional info
django	2*2	1Gi	4Gi	1000m	2000m	-	Autoscaler used (max 4 replicas)
postgres	1*1	600Mi	1000Mi	600m	1000m	15Gi	
celery worker	2*2	1Gi	2Gi	500m	1000m	-	Autoscaler used (max 4 replicas)
celery beat	1*1	100Mi	200Mi	10m	20m	-	
rabbit	1*1		600Mi		600m	2Gi	Default memory/cpu settings: Quota, requests, limits ⁷
elastic	1*1	500Mi	1000Mi	500m	1000m	21Gi	

⁵ <https://docs.openshift.com/container-platform/3.11/architecture/index.html>

⁶ https://docs.openshift.com/container-platform/3.11/architecture/infrastructure_components/kubernetes_infrastructure.html#architecture-infrastructure-components-kubernetes-infrastructure

⁷ <https://docs.psncl.pl/display/PAAS/Quota%2C+requests%2C+limits>

<i>virtuoso</i>	<i>1*1</i>		<i>600Mi</i>		<i>600m</i>	<i>6Gi</i>	<i>Default memory/cpu settings: Quota, requests, limits</i>
<i>minio</i>	<i>1*1</i>		<i>600Mi</i>		<i>600m</i>	<i>25Gi</i>	<i>Default memory/cpu settings: Quota, requests, limits</i>
<i>varnish</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>256Mi</i>	<i>512Mi</i>	<i>100m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	-	

3.5.2 ROHub production instance

Host: <https://api.rohub.org/api/>

Version: v2.0.22

Date: 14.12.2021

Browsable API root: <https://api.rohub.org/api/>

Swagger interface: <https://api.rohub.org/api/swagger/>

Redoc interface: <https://api.rohub.org/api/redoc/>

Portal: <https://reliance.rohub.org/>

ROHub IAM: <https://login.rohub.org/>

ROHub production uses as default storage for internal resources a AWS S3 service (as for now), with a capacity of 5GB.

Table 2 ROHub resources for production instance

<i>Container</i>	<i>PODS and Replicas</i>	<i>Requested Memory</i>	<i>Memory limit</i>	<i>Requested CPU</i>	<i>CPU limit</i>	<i>Storage</i>	<i>Additional info</i>
<i>django</i>	<i>2*2</i>	<i>1Gi</i>	<i>4Gi</i>	<i>1000m</i>	<i>2000m</i>	-	<i>Autoscaler used (max 4 replicas)</i>
<i>postgres</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>600Mi</i>	<i>1000Mi</i>	<i>600m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	<i>15Gi</i>	
<i>celery worker</i>	<i>2*2</i>	<i>1Gi</i>	<i>2Gi</i>	<i>500m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	-	<i>Autoscaler used (max 4 replicas)</i>
<i>celery beat</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>100Mi</i>	<i>200Mi</i>	<i>10m</i>	<i>20m</i>	-	
<i>rabbit</i>	<i>1*1</i>		<i>600Mi</i>		<i>600m</i>	<i>2Gi</i>	<i>Default memory/cpu settings: Quota, requests, limits⁸</i>

⁸ <https://docs.pnsc.pl/display/PAAS/Quota%2C+requests%2C+limits>

<i>elastic</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>500Mi</i>	<i>1000Mi</i>	<i>500m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	<i>21Gi</i>	
<i>virtuoso</i>	<i>1*1</i>		<i>600Mi</i>		<i>600m</i>	<i>6Gi</i>	<i>Default memory/cpu settings: Quota, requests, limits</i>
<i>varnish</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>256Mi</i>	<i>512Mi</i>	<i>100m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	-	

3.6 ROHub monitoring/availability

ROHub application is automatically built and deployed using Jenkins⁹ for continuous integration, and it is being monitored by a Sentry application¹⁰. Sentry is a crash reporting platform that provides real-time insight into production deployments with information to reproduce and fix crashes. It sends notifications about exceptions or errors that users run into while using the monitored application, and organises them on a web dashboard (see Figure 7). Sentry not only allows to trace errors, but also to manage them, e.g., prioritise, assign to developers, and reproduce. When the user opens a particular issue, a detailed error trace is provided to facilitate the identification and fixing of the source problem (see Figure 8), including source operating system, browser application and its version, full stack trace, and database queries.

Figure 7 Sentry dashboard for ROHub

⁹ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

¹⁰ <https://sentry.io/>

Figure 8 Detailed event information in Sentry

ROHub project' objects are backed up by Velero service¹¹. Moreover, Only annotated volumes are backed up on file system level, for which archives are created. In the case of ROHub this concerns Virtuoso and PostgreSQL. The tests proved even database volumes can be successfully restored and thus a functioning database can be resurrected. Backups take place according to defined schedules described below:

- Once a month with with 2 years retency
- Once a week with a month retency
- Once a day with two weeks retency

Paas (production environment):

- Backups are done: 0:00 AM UTC.

Paas-dev (development environment):

- Backups are done: 1:00 AM UTC.

Currently, only administrators can restore projects and volume data.

3.7 ROHub helpdesk and support channels

The official ROHub support email is support@rohub.org. Additionally, PSNC has deployed a full service desk for ROHub on top of its Jira installation. The service desk is accessible via:

¹¹ <https://velero.io/>

<https://support.pcss.pl/servicesdesk/customer/portal/27> , and include the following options (as depicted in Figure 9):

- **Licensing and Payment Questions:** for questions about licensing or billing. ROHub is provided as an online public service provided for free to researchers, scientists, students and other science enthusiasts¹², but can also be provided, with a fee, as on-site installations, or via dedicated cloud instances.
- **Other questions:** for any other questions if user can't find what they are looking for
- **Questions about the trial version of the product:** for questions related to onsite installations of ROHub.
- **Reporting a bug / functionality:** for reporting problems with ROHub
- **Suggest a new feature:** to suggest new features to be added in ROHub
- **Suggest an improvement:** to suggest something to be improved
- **Technical Support:** to get support in creating research objects, maintaining them, or troubleshooting.

Figure 9 ROHub service desk

¹² In EOSC it is provided free conditionally where users are granted access based on defined policies; such policies usually apply to Resources being offered with “sponsored use” to meet some national or EU level objective; for instance, a country may offer Resources with “sponsored use” to support national researchers involved in international collaborations

Accessing the helpdesk from the URL address above requires users to log-in into PSNC’s Jira. If the users don't have an account they can create it from the login page. This, however, may be too time consuming for a typical user trying to report just a bug/problem. Hence, we have connected ROHub support email with the helpdesk, allowing users to simply send their issue/question to the official support email. Accordingly, an email to support@rohub.org will i) create a new ticket in the ROHub service desk with a description containing the email body, and ii) generate a notification email that is sent to the ROHub support team. Each reply to the email thread i) is added as a comment in the ticket (see Figure 10), and ii) generates a notification email that is sent to other parties.

Figure 10 ROHub service desk ticket created via email

3.8 Other research object services

As depicted in Figure 1, ROHub integrates other RO added value services. In the following we describe their deployment and operation, except for the Enrichment service which is described in more detail in Section 5.

3.8.1 Checklist service

The checklist service enables the assessment of the research object quality according to what research communities producing and reusing them consider relevant. The quality assessment is based on checklists. A checklist explicitly defines the list of requirements that must be fulfilled or assessed for a given task in a given research object (see more information in D5.2).

RELIANCE has extended and adapted an existing research object quality assessment service (called RO-Manager¹³) to integrate it with the latest ROHub platform. The service was developed in Python and exposes a simple REST API with two methods that return the result of the assessment in JSON format or in HTML format.

¹³ <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro-manager/tree/master/src/roweb>

The service is deployed in a Virtual Machine (VM) at PSNC and is accessible at: <https://sandbox.rohub.org/roevaluate2/>

The VM has the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
CPU	4 Intel class core x64
RAM	8GB
HDD	30GB
Operating system	CentOS Linux 7, Kernel version: 3.10.0-1160.42.2.el7.x86_64
Network configuration	external interface: 150.254.169.10 (internal IP: 10.21.24.131) Hostname: ev-hyla.mgmt.psncc

The checklist service is being monitored through a Nagios application¹⁴. Nagios sends notifications via email to the services support team at PSNC whenever the service is not accessible (e.g., a network problem, or machine is down), so that the issue can be solved. The service support team can also check the Nagios dashboard to check more details (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 Nagios dashboard

¹⁴ <https://www.nagios.org/>

3.8.2 Stability service

The stability service monitors the quality of research objects through time. The service evaluates different quality metrics through time, including completeness, stability, and reliability, as described in D5.2. It relies on the checklist service to evaluate the completeness, and calculates the stability and reliability metrics according to the results over time.

The service has been implemented as a Java 8 Spring Boot¹⁵ project and uses a mongoDB¹⁶ database to save checklist evaluation results (in JSON format). Every time that an evaluation is saved, the completeness is calculated and saved too, thus saving time when retrieving quality metrics. Additionally, when possible, arithmetic calculations like the evaluation stability, are performed directly in MongoDB using the aggregation pipeline operator. The service saves only the latest RO evaluation for a day.

The service is deployed in a Virtual Machine (VM) at PSNC and is currently accessible at: <https://10.21.24.136:8090/> (in future it will be accessible via <https://api.rohub.org/stability>)

The VM has the following characteristics:

Characteristic	Value
CPU	12 Intel class core x64
RAM	32GB
HDD	300GB
Operating system	CentOS Linux 7, Kernel version: 3.10.0-1160.25.1.el7.x86_64
Network configuration	external interface: 150.254.169.10 (internal IP: 10.21.24.136) Hostname: ev-demos.mgmt.psnc

Similar to checklist service, the stability service is being monitored through a Nagios application¹⁷ (see Figure 11).

The stability service includes a simple frontend to visualise the research object quality over time in a line chart, and allows comparing the quality of two research objects. This frontend is also deployed in the same VM, and is accessible at: <http://10.21.24.136:8080/frontend/> (in the future it will be accessible via <http://reliance.rohub.org/stability-gui>).

¹⁵ <https://spring.io/guides/gs/spring-boot/>

¹⁶ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

¹⁷ <https://www.nagios.org/>

3.8.3 PDF service

The PDF service is a simple service that generates a paper style view of a research object in PDF format. The goal of this service is to make it easier for outsiders and new adopters to understand research objects by providing them with a view of the research in the traditional paper style and format. See D5.2 for additional information.

The service is implemented in Python and is deployed as an additional component of ROHub in the PaaS environment. Tables 3 and 4 describe the resources associated with the service in the development and production instance of ROHub, respectively.

The service is accessible via the main ROHub API, through the endpoint `/ros/{identifier}/download`, which allows downloading a particular research object in different formats, including PDF.

Table 3 PDF service resources for development instance

<i>Container</i>	<i>Replicas</i>	<i>Requested Memory</i>	<i>Memory limit</i>	<i>Requested CPU</i>	<i>CPU limit</i>	<i>Storage</i>	<i>Additional info</i>
<i>Latex (PDF service)</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>500Mi</i>	<i>1000Mi</i>	<i>500m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	<i>3Gi</i>	

Table 4 PDF service resources for production instance

<i>Container</i>	<i>PODS and Replicas</i>	<i>Requested Memory</i>	<i>Memory limit</i>	<i>Requested CPU</i>	<i>CPU limit</i>	<i>Storage</i>	<i>Additional info</i>
<i>Latex (PDF service)</i>	<i>1*1</i>	<i>500Mi</i>	<i>1000Mi</i>	<i>500m</i>	<i>1000m</i>	<i>3Gi</i>	

4 Data Cubes

In the international scenario, Data Cubes are being progressively adopted to provide a common reference and data infrastructure for geospatial data, mostly related to the discovery, access, processing and exploitation of large collections of multi-temporal, multi-resolution satellite imagery. A Data Cube generally is represented as a multi-dimensional data artefact (which can be 1-dimensional, 2-dimensional, 3-dimensional, or higher). In general a Data Cube consists of a comprehensive set of functions:

- to describe the data structure (e.g. its spatial resolution or temporal dimensions and granularity), and more precisely
 - o Dataset: a collection of products e.g. grouped by phase mission.
 - o Product: the single file which is made available through the ADAM Space service
- to describe all the available services to exploit discovery, access, view and analytics services

In the framework of RELIANCE, the ADAM platform is used as reference implementation of Data Cube. In the first twelve (12) months, the activities have been focused on:

- Assessing the heterogeneous metadata used by the different communities in order to define the Data Cube metadata model
- Collecting user data requirements in order to prioritise the building and indexing of Data Cube resources
- Setting-up the development/operation frontend and backend services of RELIANCE Data Cube, including the integration with EOSC core services (i.e. EGI check-in)
- Developing an API package to allow scientists at consuming data cube service through a machine-2-machine interface
- Onboarding the ADAM Platform in the European Open Science Cloud infrastructure

4.1 User Interfaces and services

The RELIANCE Data Cube service offers different user interfaces and services to support non-expert users, experts in geospatial application domains, scientists as well as web developers that need a machine-to-machine interface to develop their own applications.

4.1.1 Explorer

The Explorer frontend offers a human-friendly user interface for non-expert users to discover, access and visualise data cubes in a virtual globe environment.

The EOSC/EGI check-in through the RO-Hub keycloak service (Figure 12 - left) is integrated to support the broad community of the European Open Science Cloud. Once logged in, the non-expert user can discover data cube resources (Figure 12 - middle): once a data cube resource is selected, the user can explore and visualise the content of the data cube in space and time, and extract the data at the native spatial granularity (i.e. pixel-based).

The service is available at: <https://reliance.adamplatform.eu>.

The series of OGC services supported by the DAS component are aligned with OGC Testbed17¹⁸

Figure 14 - OGC Testbed17: Conceptual model of Geo Data Cube

4.2 Data Cube resources

To support the RELIANCE user communities, a series of data cubes have been built and made available to RELIANCE and EOSC users. The table below gives the list of datacubes broken down per service release.

Table 5 RELIANCE Data Cubes

Community	Data Cube	Release (Month)
CNR	Ocean Colour Data	R1 (M6)
CNR	World Ocean Atlas 2018	R2 (M12)
CNR	CoastColour	R3 (M21)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly and Daily Interpolated Surface Chlorophyll Concentration from Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 Olci Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Surface Chlorophyll Concentration From Multi Satellite and Sentinel-3 Olci Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly And Daily Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration From Multi Satellite Observations + Seawifs Daily Climatology	R2 (M12)

¹⁸ <https://www.ogc.org/projects/initiatives/t17>

CNR	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Surface Chlorophyll Concentration And Phytoplankton Functional Types From Multi Satellite Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Monthly Attenuation Coefficient At 490nm From Multi Satellite And Sentinel-3 Olci Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Remote Sensing Reflectances And Attenuation Coefficient At 490nm From Multi Satellite And Sentinel-3 Olci Observations	R2 (M12)
CNR	Mediterranean Sea Reprocessed Remote Sensing Reflectances And Attenuation Coefficient At 490nm From Multi Satellite Observations	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-1 Single Look Complex	R3 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-1 Unwrapped interferograms and coherence maps	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Land Surface Temperature	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Aerosol Optical Depth	R2 (M12)
INGV	Sentinel-3 Top of Atmosphere Radiances and Brightness Temperature	R2 (M12)
INGV	Tandem X (DEM 90m)	R2 (M12)
INGV	SRMT (DEM 30 m)	R2 (M12)
INGV	MODIS -AQUA and MODIS-TERRA	R1 (M6)
UiO	CAMS European air quality forecasts	R1 (M6)
UiO	UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe on single levels from 1961 to 2019	R2 (M12)
UiO	Arctic regional reanalysis on single levels from 1998 to 2019	R2 (M12)
UiO	ECMWF seasonal forecast	R2 (M12)
UiO	ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis	R2 (M12)

4.3 Cloud resources

The following table enumerates the access and physical/virtual resources for the RELIANCE Data Cube service components.

Table 6 RELIANCE Data Cube service components and cloud resources

Component	Development instance	Operational instance
Explorer frontend	https://reliance-dev.adamplatform.eu	https://reliance.adamplatform.eu

	2core, 8GB RAM, 20GB HDD	4core, 16GB RAM, 100GB HDD
Jupyter	https://reliance-jupyter-dev.adamplatform.eu 2core, 8GB RAM, 100GB HDD	https://reliance-jupyter.adamplatform.eu 8core, 64GB RAM, 300GB HDD Target service: https://notebooks.egi.eu
AAA	EGI dev check-in (via RO-Hub keycloak-dev)	EGI check-in (via RO-Hub keycloak)
DAS	https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu core	
Cloud storage	200TB @ MEEO Connection with DICE if needed	
adamapi	latest	version 2.0.11

5 Text Mining and Semantic Enrichment Services

Research objects aggregate heterogeneous resources associated with a particular research activity and metadata relevant to understand and interpret their content using semantic annotations that are user and machine-readable. However, most of the semantic annotations in a research object describe its structure and the type of resources it aggregates and few metadata is concerned with the actual payload of the research object. Without metadata about the content, the vision of automatic or at least assisted processing of scientific information using research objects is unfeasible. The lack of research object content annotations limits the potential outreach and diffusion of scientific outcomes, ultimately hampering reuse by other researchers.

The text mining and enrichment services in Reliance focus on extracting and structuring valuable information from textual resources contained in research objects. However, research object content can also be multimodal, containing a mix of text, data, images and code. Addressing the automatic processing of multimodal information is still an open research problem subject to future work.

During this period, three main services have been developed in Reliance to address the above-mentioned challenges related to automatically adding and exploiting content-based metadata in research objects (more information on each individual service can be found in deliverable D3.2v1):

- **enrichment service**, which extracts such metadata from the resources contained in a research object and
- **Two information retrieval services for research object search and recommendation** that enhance research object findability and access based on such metadata.

Figure 15: Landing page of the Reliance text mining and enrichment services, available at <https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai>

The functionalities provided by all such services have been integrated with ROHub and are available through individual APIs from the EOSC marketplace.

Figure 16: Services onboarded in EOSC (<https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/dashboard/expertai/resources>)

5.1 Enrichment service

The semantic enrichment process is in charge of generating new metadata out of the text content of files or collections of files, such as research objects. Such metadata comprise:

- **Main concepts** found in resources containing text.
- **Main knowledge areas or domains** in which such concepts are most frequently used.
- **Main expressions**, known in computational linguistics as **noun phrases**, found in the text.
- **Named entities**, which can be further refined as people, organisations, and places.

The core of the semantic enrichment process is **expert.ai NL technology**. Expert.ai uses a knowledge graph called Sensigrafo¹⁹, which is conceptually similar to WordNet²⁰ where words are grouped into concepts with other words sharing the same meaning, and the concepts are related between them by means of explicit linguistic relations, such as hypernyms or hyponyms among many others.. The semantics of the extracted metadata is explicit, since the concepts are grounded to the knowledge graph. Information retrieval processes, including search engines and recommendation systems, benefit from working at a conceptual level rather than based on keywords, mainly as these support disambiguation and help providing a more complete and accurate set of results, enabling the exploration of research object collections, e.g. by means of facets where the semantic metadata is available.

The enrichment service deployed in EOSC addresses both the annotation of individual documents and of research objects as aggregations of resources that may contain text. Next we describe both aspects and their corresponding APIs.

5.1.1 Document enrichment

¹⁹ <https://www.expert.ai/products/technology/knowledge-graph>

²⁰ <https://wordnet.princeton.edu>

Document Enrichment extends expert.ai Natural Language API (NL API) to process the text extracted from scientific documents, particularly in Earth Science and Earth Observation. The NL API is a cloud-based software service providing a comprehensive set of natural language understanding capabilities. These capabilities include linguistic tasks such as part-of-speech, morphological analysis, lemmatizations, syntactic analysis, and semantic analysis. In addition, the NL API can perform sentiment analysis, text classification and the extraction of key phrases, named entities, and relations.

The Document Enrichment service is a RESTful API which receives a file with text as an input and generates relevant annotations following the workflow described in Figure 17. The service accepts plain text files, Word documents, PDF files, and PowerPoint files. Other formats, such as Jupyter notebooks, readme files or data cubes text content are also in our roadmap. When a request for the enrichment of a document is issued, the service extracts the raw text from the document, using Apache PDFBox²¹ in the case of PDF files and Apache POI²² in the case of Word and PowerPoint files. Then, such text is automatically annotated. Each metadata piece is associated with a score indicating its relevance in the context of the overall document.

Figure 17: Document enrichment process

The different metadata types, including main concepts, expressions, entities and domains, are added to the response as annotations in a turtle file. The annotations are written according to the content description vocabulary (<https://w3id.org/contentdesc>). Below an example of how the service can be called and the results that it provides is presented.

```
curl -X POST -F 'file=@dModels.pdf' https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/eosc/enrichment
{
  "filename": "dModels.pdf",
  "lang": "en",
  "domains": {
    "mathematics": 17.7,
    "geometry": 7.1,
    "geology": 26.7
  },
  "expressions": {
```

²¹ <https://pdfbox.apache.org>

²² <https://poi.apache.org>

```

"GPS deformation velocity": 2.6,
"GPS horizontal": 1.8,
"ITRF wgs ellipsoid": 2,
"geology of Augustine volcano": 14,
"volcano Science Center": 1.8,
"inflation of a dipping finite prolate spheroid": 7.7,
"dMODELS software package implementations": 4.4,
"fault geometry parameter": 2.1,
"Long Valley caldera": 2.4,
"ITRF coordinate": 1.5,
"volcano deformation source": 2.5,
"Princeton University press": 28.2,
"Journal of Geophysical Research": 13.2,
"dMODELS software package": 4.5,
"software availability": 1.3,
"deformation from inflation": 10.8,
"volcano sourceSphere magma chamber McTigue": 3.9,
"fault slip": 2.5,
"MATLAB software package": 2.1,
"volcano deformation": 1.2,
"WorldGeodetic System": 1.8,
"Department of Defense WorldGeodetic system": 1.2,
"software package dMODELS": 2.3
},
"people": {},
"places": {
  "Augustine Volcano": 2,
  "Augustine": 2,
  "New York": 1,
  "United States of America": 5,
  "Waitt": 1,
  "Menlo Park": 1,
  "January eruption of Augustine Volcano": 1,
  "California": 5,
  "Cook Inlet": 1,
  "McTigue": 3,
  "Sill Fialko": 1,
  "Rome": 1,
  "Valley": 1,
  "Long": 2,
  "Alaska": 5,
  "Menlo Park": 3
},
"org": {
  "Seismological Society of America": 3,
  "Ministry of Defence": 1,
  "Defense Mapping Agency": 3,
  "Sapienza University of Rome": 1,
  "Princeton University": 2,
  "United States Department of Earth Science": 1,
  "U.S. Geological Survey": 8,
  "National Imagery and Mapping Agency": 4,
},

```

```

"concepts": {
  "datum": 5.3,
  "data": 5.1,
  "software": 14.8,
  "geology": 6.6,
  "inflation": 6.7,
  "chemise": 4.5,
  "conduit": 4.9,
  "Princeton University": 6.6,
  "caldera": 6,
  "parametric quantity": 5.9,
  "parameter": 7.1,
  "deformation": 4.3,
  "Alaska": 6.5,
  "volcano": 10.8,
  "coordinate system": 6.9,
  "coordinate": 4.1,
  "magma chamber": 6.4,
  "fault": 5.3,
  "California": 6,
  "velocity": 8.1,
  "global positioning system": 6.1,
  "spheroid": 8.6,
  "system": 5.1,
  "U.S. Geological Survey": 5.8,
  "half-space": 10.5,
  "statistics": 9.8
}
}

```

5.1.2 Research object enrichment

To enrich a research object with metadata extracted from its content, the research object enrichment service is called at the same url (<https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/ro/enrichment>), indicating as a parameter the research object URI. The request is not served in real time but submitted to a queueing system built on RabbitMQ²³ that serialises the different, potentially parallel requests. The research object enrichment process is described in Figure 18. The service first extracts the resources from the research object using the ROHub API, then such resources are filtered considering the resource type and sent to the Document enrichment service to get the semantic annotations. Since each resource is described with a set of annotations we need to aggregate them to generate a unique set of annotations representative for the research object. The metadata resulting from each individual resource is then aggregated at the research object level. Below, we show an example of how the service can be called:

```

curl -X POST https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/ro/enrichment -d
  '{"ro_uri": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/1cf5502c-c693-4ba6-b884-63cbb9afb2e5",
  "callback": "https://api.rohub.org/api/service/enrichment/callback/",
  "nonce": "gAAAAABgpDWH0iihSiHo2ziTtLnMSLiiHMFyt5TTgozyzR[...]"
  }'

```

²³ <https://www.rabbitmq.com>

Figure 18: Research object enrichment process

5.2 Search service

The Search engine is based on a Solr²⁴ index of the collection of research objects from ROHub that have been previously enriched. These annotations, added to the original metadata of the research object, are leveraged to produce more accurate results and to provide new facets to explore the research object collection. This index is also at the core of the Recommendation API, which proposes relevant research objects given a collection of research objects or researchers.

The Solr index follows a schema which accommodates the metadata obtained from ROHub and the annotations generated by the enrichment service for each research object. It has the same six different facets as the enrichment service: Concepts, domains, expressions, people, places and organisations. These facet fields, along with the rest of documents hosted by the index, are updated every time a research object is created or updated in ROHub. Moreover, each indexed item includes additional related information, such as the title, description and creator of the research object, which can be accessed through the Solr API.

The index is built on a Solr version 8.9.0 and can be accessed using the SolrJ²⁵ API or sending queries right to the service. To this purpose, it is necessary to login with a standard user account, which allows running search queries against the index. More information about how the Solr API works or which type of queries can be sent to this service can be found on the official Solr site.²⁶

Next, we show an example that illustrates how to call the service through the available API. The following query consists of a json document with the research objects which contains the word "carrot":

²⁴ <https://solr.apache.org>

²⁵ https://solr.apache.org/guide/6_6/using-solrj.html

²⁶ https://solr.apache.org/guide/8_9/solr-tutorial.html

```
curl --user standard_user:standard_user -H "Content-Type: application/json"
https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/solr/ROHub/select?q=carrot
```

```
{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":0,
    "params":{
      "q":"carrot"
    }
  },
  "response":{
    "numFound":1,
    "start":0,
    "numFoundExact":true,
    "docs":[
      {
        "id":"https://w3id.org/ro-id/ed4689fc-7772-4f61-8510-a5c07076c2f1",
        "title":"Carrot",
        "autocomplete":[
          "Carrot",
          "Gosia Wolniewicz",
          "Food and Agriculture Organization",
          "Iran",
          "Europe",
          "carrot salad",
          "carrot",
          "carrot family",
          "botany"
        ],
        "description":"The carrot (Daucus carota subsp. sativus) is a root vegetable, most commonly observed as orange in color, though purple, black, red, white, and yellow cultivars exist,[2][3][4] all of which are domesticated forms of the wild carrot, Daucus carota, native to Europe and Southwestern Asia. The plant probably originated in Persia and was originally cultivated for its leaves and seeds. The most commonly eaten part of the plant is the taproot, although the stems and leaves are also eaten. The domestic carrot has been selectively bred for its greatly enlarged, more palatable, less woody-textured taproot.\n\nThe carrot is a biennial plant in the umbellifer family, Apiaceae. At first, it grows a rosette of leaves while building up the enlarged taproot. Fast-growing cultivars mature within three months (90 days) of sowing the seed, while slower-maturing cultivars need a month longer (120 days). The roots contain high quantities of alpha- and beta-carotene, and are a good source of vitamin K and vitamin B6.\n\nThe United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) reports that world production of carrots and turnips (these plants are combined by the FAO) for 2018 was 40 million tonnes, with 45% of the world total grown in China. Carrots are widely used in many cuisines, especially in the preparation of salads, and carrot salads are a tradition in many regional cuisines.",
        "creator":"https://w3id.org/users/gosiaw",
        "author":"Gosia Wolniewicz",
        "source_ro":"https://w3id.org/ro-id/ed4689fc-7772-4f61-8510-a5c07076c2f1",
        "sketch":"https://api.rohub.org/api/resources/dc5beea9-2559-4632-a7fe-84261ba1686b/download/",
        "organization":[
          "Food and Agriculture Organization"
        ],
        "place":[
          "Iran",
          "Europe"
        ],
        "concepts":[
          "carrot",
```

```

        "carrot family"
      ],
      "domains":[
        "botany"
      ],
      "content":"Carrot The carrot (Daucus carota subsp. sativus) is a root
vegetable, most commonly observed as orange in color, though purple, black, red,
white, and yellow cultivars exist,[2][3][4] all of which are domesticated forms of the
wild carrot, Daucus carota, native to Europe and Southwestern Asia. The plant probably
originated in Persia and was originally cultivated for its leaves and seeds. The most
commonly eaten part of the plant is the taproot, although the stems and leaves are
also eaten. The domestic carrot has been selectively bred for its greatly enlarged,
more palatable, less woody-textured taproot.\n\nThe carrot is a biennial plant in the
umbellifer family, Apiaceae. At first, it grows a rosette of leaves while building up
the enlarged taproot. Fast-growing cultivars mature within three months (90 days) of
sowing the seed, while slower-maturing cultivars need a month longer (120 days). The
roots contain high quantities of alpha- and beta-carotene, and are a good source of
vitamin K and vitamin B6.\n\nThe United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization
(FAO) reports that world production of carrots and turnips (these plants are combined
by the FAO) for 2018 was 40 million tonnes, with 45% of the world total grown in
China. Carrots are widely used in many cuisines, especially in the preparation of
salads, and carrot salads are a tradition in many regional cuisines. Gosia Wolniewicz
Food and Agriculture Organization Iran Europe carrot salad
net.expertsystem.everest.new_enricher.processor.CustomizedSyncon@d946
net.expertsystem.everest.new_enricher.processor.CustomizedSyncon@5f81aa1 botany ",
      "compound_terms":[
        "carrot salad"
      ],
      "_version_":1708622095565455360
    }
  ]
}
}
}

```

Next, the following example illustrates how to use the Search service to do faceted search. In this case, we search for all the research objects which have "fertiliser" as one of their main concepts.

```

curl --user standard_user:standard_user -H "Content-Type: application/json"
"https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/solr/ROHub/select?fq=concepts:fertiliser&q=:*"

```

```

{
  "responseHeader":{
    "status":0,
    "QTime":0,
    "params":{
      "q":":*",
      "fq":"concepts:fertiliser"
    }
  },
  "response":{
    "numFound":1,
    "start":0,
    "numFoundExact":true,
    "docs":[
      {
        "id":"https://w3id.org/ro-id/f7c99782-4caa-48dc-b7ce-7dd4a4f0d5af",
        "title":"In My Backyard",
        "autocomplete":[
          "In My Backyard",
          "Esteban Gonzlez",

```


5.6 Text mining and enrichment services support channel

There is an official email address where users can report any issue or question related to these services to our helpdesk: helpdesk.reliance@expert.ai

6 Earth Observation Data Pipelines

The Copernicus Earth Observation Data Pipeline is an integrated intermediate service layer for the systematic execution of Earth Observation Applications continuously delivering data and information to users. A data pipeline is the solution provided to a specific data challenge defined by a researcher as a tailored data processing workflow responsible for information extraction from a wide range of large volume data sources that are executed within defined spatial and temporal intervals.

Integrating Copernicus data and services into the service catalogue of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) provides researchers with access to the data of the Sentinel missions and information from the Copernicus services in a sustainable alternative to existing Copernicus DIAS. By federating existing research infrastructures and scientific clouds, the EOSC offers an open pan-European virtual environment to access, store, analyse and reuse data, and can support the development of cloud-based services for Earth Science using Earth Observation data.

As such, EOSC can offer an integrated virtual environment to deposit, share and reuse EO data and can even provide the computing resources necessary to manipulate and manage large amounts of Copernicus data. By making it easier to retrieve and process EO data, EOSC could stimulate demand for EO research, services and market opportunities for EO data services.

This section documents the implementation and deployment of Copernicus Data Pipelines for RELIANCE users provided by Terradue Ellip Platform²⁹. The activities include the application package process [3] and the technical and operational choices for computer resource provisioning and EO data sourcing strategy, deployment and data production onto Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) providers from EOSC. With Ellip, the Data Pipeline uses shared data processing infrastructures from EOSC where the applications are deployed, providing a hybrid and reliable Cloud infrastructure for application needs. Terradue Ellip Platform manages the IaaS and Cloud resources, orchestrates the execution of the triggered Data Pipelines and publishes the results.

Figure 20- GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory Areas of Interest

During this 1st year of the project, the activities focused on INGV's use cases preparing the response to *Scenario 1* (analysing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions) and *Scenario 2* (developing models and creating a new specific workflow to analyse SAR data). It was identified the need to provide data pipelines accessing long time series of Copernicus Data for the GEO Geohazard

²⁹ <https://ellip.terradue.com/>

Supersites (represented in RELIANCE by the INGV). The GEO Geohazard Supersites and Natural Laboratory initiative³⁰ (GSNL) is a voluntary international partnership aiming to improve, through an Open Science approach, geophysical scientific research and geohazard assessment in support of Disaster Risk Reduction. It is focused in different regions as shown in Figure 20.

The data requirements are focused on the Copernicus Sentinel-1 SLC Products³¹ (S1A + S1B Full mission) crossing the Supersites locations and we calculated the storage size needed at 358TB (with a subsequent 78TB yearly volume update).

6.1 Data Sourcing

The EO Data Pipelines are basically the scheduled execution of EO Applications, where the systematic processing is fed by EO data products, be it in a data time driven or data driven, backward or forward looking. While Open Data policies are becoming commonplace for the Earth observation domain, some technical challenges still remain to efficiently store, curate and serve such datasets to be deployed as Data Pipelines. Also, user applications might have to compose with multiple data sources having different types of dissemination and exploitation policies, and user support must be provided in this perspective.

Nevertheless, as Sentinel data moves from online to ordering mechanism it is necessary to deploy Virtual Archives where the data access is provided directly from the infrastructure (mirrored), or it can be fetched and cached in the infrastructure with adjustable time window and caching policy, or it can be routed directly to a remote data provider facility. The approach also includes a data preparation feature that may increase the internal data throughput, avoiding bottlenecks by staging the data for the tasked processes.

To respond to use cases we started the ingestion of Sentinel-1 data (potentially extended to Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3 and Landsat-8 in the future). We conceived it to support two basic scenarios:

- Opportunistic - where data ingestion is (manually) triggered by the user in response to a specific need / event .
- Systematic - where data ingestion is performed automatically for a given community / stakeholder on top of a data hosting framework.

To respond to the immediate data storage needs of the use cases we established a collaboration with the DICE-EOSC³² project established cache for specific areas identified by the GEO Geohazard Supersites. This will allow us to access the full time series of Sentinel-1 Data SLC products for those locations (initially ~ 320 TB with a subsequent ~70 TB yearly volume update) through object storage accessible via HTTPS and compatible with S3.

The following table enumerates the different Supersites, their geographic area and approximative number of Sentinel-1 SLC products that are currently being cached at CESNET.

Table 7 GSNL Location and number of Sentinel-1 products

³⁰ <https://geo-gsnl.org/>

³¹ <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/technical-guides/sentinel-1-sar/products-algorithms/level-1-algorithms/single-look-complex>

³² <https://www.dice-eosc.eu/>

GSNL Name	Number of Products	Yearly Update	Area of Interest (WKT)
China	~6700	~1360	POLYGON ((99.63 25.5, 104.02 25.44, 104.76 31.91, 99.92 32.03, 99.63 25.5))
Ecuadorian Volcanoes	~2200	~420	POLYGON ((-78.21 0.52, -78.37 0.41, -78.66 -0.08, -78.9 -0.63, -78.96 -0.88, -78.99 -1.4, -78.94 -1.78, -78.43 -2.09, -78.22 -2.1, -78.32 -1.81, -78.28 -1.29, -78.09 -0.82, -77.7 -0.28, -77.6 -0.07, -77.54 0.36, -77.49 0.54, -77.68 0.65, -77.65 0.68, -77.96 0.85, -78.21 0.52))
EnCeladus Hellenic	~5800	~1080	POLYGON ((19.28 37.82, 24.18 37.23, 24.58 38.64, 19.6 39.32, 19.28 37.82))
Hawaiian Volcanoes	~1800	~410	POLYGON ((-156.14 19.77, -155.98 19.06, -155.66 18.83, -154.67 19.51, -155.2 20.08, -155.94 20.37, -156.14 19.77))
Icelandic Volcanoes	~5400	~1060	POLYGON ((-22.99 63.7, -20.82 63.7, -20.78 63.2, -19.1 63.19, -15.2 64.2, -16.58 66.4, -18.22 66.35, -17.45 65.19, -19.35 64.4, -22.99 64.4, -22.99 63.7))
Kamchatka	~5900	~1280	POLYGON ((152.84 48.03, 154.06 47.74, 165.86 56.96, 156.9 58.7, 152.84 48.03))
Marmara Region	~8300	~1490	POLYGON ((26 39, 31 39, 31 42, 26 41.99, 26 39))
Mt Etna	~2200	~430	POLYGON ((14.5 37.3, 15.5 37.3, 15.5 38, 14.5 38, 14.5 37.3))
New Zealand Volcanoes	~2000	~460	POLYGON ((177.55 -37.32, 176.56 -36.98, 174.97 -39.36, 175.89 -39.77, 177.55 -37.32))
Nicaragua Volcanoes	~1300	~270	POLYGON ((-87.38 13.28, -87.76 12.94, -85.71 11.2, -85.32 11.49, -87.38 13.28))
San Andreas Fault Natural Laboratory	~11800	~2900	POLYGON ((-125.73 41.49, -124.11 38.33, -122.2 35.73, -120.16 33.55, -116.51 31.52, -112.87 31.48, -116.6 35.24, -118.81 36.21, -122.84 41.99, -125.73 41.49))
Southern Andes	~1700	~350	POLYGON ((-72.16 -39.75, -71.44 -39.74, -70.97 -37.76, -71.61 -37.74, -72.16 -39.75))
Vesuvius - Campi Flegrei	~1700	~310	POLYGON ((13.96 40.76, 14.55 40.75, 14.55 40.94, 13.96 40.94, 13.96 40.76))
Virunga	~1000	~210	POLYGON ((28.49 -2.53, 29.47 -2.79, 30 -0.99, 29.06 -0.76, 28.49 -2.53))

The availability of that storage will allow us to perform:

- ingestion and cataloguing of data (metadata extraction and publication)
- organisation and transformation of data (STAC, COG)
- data calibration and creation of data visualisations

With the data ingestion and cataloguing activity it is possible for the users to discover the data through the STAC API, the dynamic version of a STAC JSON file. This API returns a STAC *Catalog*, *Collection*, *Item*, or a STAC API *ItemCollection*, depending on the endpoint and enables complex queries to be performed by the users. We deployed a STAC API instance³³ where the data described in Table 7 is being registered and made available for discovery.

³³ <https://reliance-stac.terradue.com/>

As one of the main objectives in RELIANCE is the use of Jupyter Notebooks as the default working and computing environment for researchers, we also developed several documentation and examples on how to discover (Figure 21 and 22) , access and analyse EO products directly from a Notebook.

```

16): for index, elem in enumerate(items_json['features']):
    coords = elem['geometry']
    coords_poly = Polygon(
        locations=np.asarray([t[::-1] for t in list(coords['coordinates'])[0])).tolist(),
        color='red',
        fill_opacity=0,
        weight=1
    )
    m.add_layer(coords_poly)
    m

```


Figure 21 - Displaying the STAC API query result on an interactive map directly in a Jupyter Notebook

```

128): result = []
locations = []

for index, elem in enumerate(items_json['features']):
    bbox = box(elem['bbox'][0],
               elem['bbox'][1],
               elem['bbox'][2],
               elem['bbox'][3])
    locations.append([t[::-1] for t in list.loads(bbox.wkt).exterior.coords])
    slave_wkt = loads(bbox.wkt)
    result.append({'id': elem['id'],
                  'datetime': elem['properties']['datetime'],
                  'pos': elem['properties']['satellite_position'],
                  'rel_orb': elem['properties']['satrelative_orbit'],
                  'wkt': loads(bbox.wkt)
                  })

slaves = gpd.GeoDataFrame(result)
slaves

```

	id	datetime	pos	rel_orb	wkt
0	SIA_IW_SLC_ISDV_20171115T050436_20171115T0505...	2017-11-15T05:04:36.625761Z	[VV, VH]	124	POLYGON ((16.288458 36.604851, 16.288456 38.62...
1	SIA_IW_SLC_ISDV_20171103T050436_20171103T0505...	2017-11-03T05:04:36.894865Z	[VV, VH]	124	POLYGON ((16.287598 36.604884, 16.287596 38.62...
2	SIA_IW_SLC_ISDV_20171022T050436_20171022T0505...	2017-10-22T05:04:36.950392Z	[VV, VH]	124	POLYGON ((16.28792 36.604164, 16.28792 38.6290...
3	SIA_IW_SLC_ISDV_20171010T050436_20171010T0505...	2017-10-10T05:04:36.891212Z	[VV, VH]	124	POLYGON ((16.287987 36.602926, 16.287987 38.62...
4	SIA_IW_SLC_ISDV_20170928T050436_20170928T0505...	2017-09-28T05:04:36.650762Z	[VV, VH]	124	POLYGON ((16.288161 36.603657, 16.288161 38.62...

Figure 22 - Loading specific fields of the STAC API query result to a data frame in a Jupyter Notebook

6.2 Processing Resources

The Copernicus Data Pipelines use shared data processing infrastructures where the applications are deployed. The service manages the IaaS and Cloud resources, orchestrates the execution of the triggered Data Pipelines and publishes the results.

Working with Cloud-hosted data requires the availability of interfaces, APIs and tools that will alleviate the burden for operators when it comes to deploy and execute the Data Pipeline. With Kubernetes, the platform is able to dynamically respond to such changes by distributing the processing and analysis on a variable number of nodes (i.e. scaling out) and/or adding more storage space, to ensure the response time stays within a reasonable limit. Kubernetes is a Container orchestration system for automating application deployment, scaling and management fully compatible with the EO Application Package Best Practice [3].

Every software unit is packaged as containers and deployed on a Kubernetes infrastructure managed by Helm charts and supervised by a Continuous Deployment tool. All system components are able to scale according to the processing load at every stage: download, harvesting, pre-processing and synthetic/systematic product.

PSNC is providing the necessary resources for Kubernetes infrastructure requirements with the initial definition of the nodes with :

- 8 VCPUs
- 32 GB of memory RAM
- Storage class to ensure data persistence of at least 100GB SSD

7 Other services

7.1 EGI Notebooks

One of the main objectives in RELIANCE is the use of Jupyter Notebooks as the default working and computing environment for researchers. Jupyter Notebook (and its JupyterLab)³⁴ is one of the most popular web-based interactive computing platforms for scientists. The JupyterLab provides a flexible interface that allows users to configure and arrange workflows in data science, scientific computing, computational journalism, machine learning and other areas.

RELIANCE is leveraging another EOSC service, namely EGI Notebooks³⁵, to provide its users a flexible and scalable Jupyter Notebooks environment. In order to get this environment, RELIANCE requested its own community (aka Virtual Organisation - VO) in EGI Notebooks, initially with resources for 10 concurrent users (4 GB RAM per user), which is accessible at the moment only by scientists from the RELIANCE research communities (currently the research community partners, but this will be extended after the open call).

In order for a user to get access to the RELIANCE VO in EGI Notebooks he must follow a few simple steps:

- Get an account in <https://aai.egi.eu/> (for new EOSC users)
- Join the vo.reliance-project.eu VO via: https://aai.egi.eu/registry/co_petitions/start/coef:317
- Start using the service via: <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>

Once the user authenticates in the service, he will see two server options (as depicted in Figure 23). As part of the ongoing analysis of research communities in RELIANCE, we may create custom server options tailored to the specific community needs, which will pre-load the libraries typically used by a particular community.

Figure 23 EGI Notebooks loading page for RELIANCE VO

After selecting a server option, the environment is loaded and the user can choose what to load (e.g., a Python Notebook) or open (e.g., an existing notebook) to start working (see Figure 24)

³⁴ <https://jupyter.org/>

³⁵ <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>

Figure 24 EGI Notebook launcher options for RELIANCE VO

7.2 EGI DataHub

RELIANCE is also leveraging EGI DataHub³⁶, another EOSC service, to facilitate the sharing of data between scientists in the research communities, and to provide a data storage space where they can store intermediate/working data.

EGI DataHub enables the discovery of data via a central portal, as well as access to data conforming to required policies, which may be: unauthenticated open access; access after user registration or access restricted to members of a Virtual Organization (VO). Additionally, EGI DataHub's Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) is integrated with EGI check-in, and is connected with other EGI components.

EGI DataHub created a RELIANCE space, initially of 100GB, which is accessible only by members of the RELIANCE VO. Hence, after authenticating in EGI DataHub, RELIANCE users are able to see this space from the central portal (see Figure 25). Moreover, this storage space is directly accessible from EGI Notebooks (see Figure 26) so that RELIANCE users can easily share resources, including Jupyter Notebooks, directly from the computing environment. As these resources can be shared via public links, they can also be aggregated in research objects.

³⁶ <https://datahub.egi.eu/>

Figure 25 EGI DataHub central portal with RELIANCE space

Figure 26 EGI Notebook with access to RELIANCE space in EGI DataHub

7.3 VM on demand

In addition to the infrastructure where RELIANCE services are deployed and running, RELIANCE also provides additional VMs to some of the research communities, which are used by scientists to run and execute their own applications and tools, e.g., to do specific data analysis or simulations. These

resources are currently provided by PSNC, however, a future goal is to leverage EOSC resources, in particular EGI compute cloud³⁷. This could include services for VM on demand for the scientists, and potentially for (some of the) RELIANCE services, enabling the scaling-out and growing horizontally to support a larger number of users.

The current set of resources allocated in PSNC for VMs on demand are split into two OpenStack projects. The first project has allocated 128 VCPUs, 320GB RAM and ~10TB of storage (see Figure 27). The second project has allocated 200 VCPUs, 340GB RAM and ~50TB of storage (see Figure 28).

Figure 27 RELIANCE project (DCW) in OpenStack showing resources allocated by PSNC for providers/users

Figure 28 RELIANCE project (BST) in OpenStack showing resources allocated by PSNC for providers/users

More in detail regarding the VMs for RELIANCE researchers, PSNC has created 10 VMs, including 8 for the supersites community (INGV) and 2 for the sea monitoring community (CNR-ISMAR). The first OpenStack project includes one VM for CNR-ISMAR (see Figure 29), which has the following configuration:

³⁷ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-cloud-compute?q=EGI+Cloud+Compute>

Characteristic	Value
CPU	32 Intel class core x64
RAM	64GB
HDD	50GB (main storage) + external storage of 250GB
Operating system	Ubuntu (version 20.04.3 LTS)
Network configuration	external interface: 195.216.97.38

Figure 29 OpenStack project showing VM of CNR-ISMAR

The second OpenStack project includes 8 VMs for INGV and one of CNR-ISMAR (see Figure 30 and 31). Each INGV VM has the following configuration:

Characteristic	Value
CPU	16 Intel class core x64
RAM	32GB
HDD	90GB (main storage) + external storage of 1TB (3 out of 8) or 3TB (5 out of 8)
Operating system	Windows 10
Network configuration	external interface: 62.3.170.xx

While the CNR-ISMAR VM has the following configuration:

Characteristic	Value
CPU	8 Intel class core x64
RAM	16GB
HDD	200GB (main storage)
Operating system	Windows 7 pro
Network configuration	external interface: 150.254.165.42

Figure 30 OpenStack project showing one VM of CNR-ISMAR and 8 for INGV

Figure 31 OpenStack project showing volumes (external storage) attached to INGV VMs

References

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